

PartArt40W

PARTART
40W

Art & Oceans

PartArt4OW

Data and Ethics Management Plan

Deliverable 1.2

Funded by
the European Union

Innovate
UK

Deliverable description

Deliverable	D1.2 Data and Ethics Management Plan
Work Package	1 - Project coordination and management
Due of Deliverable	28.02.2025
Lead beneficiary of this deliverable	University of Sapienza of Rome
Version	V1.0
Author(s) and institution(s)	Luca Bertocci, Chiara Certomà, Caterina Pozzobon - University of Sapienza of Rome
Submission Date	14.01.2025
External Reviewer	Gefion Thuermer
Internal Reviewer	Maria Hadjimichael
PU	Public
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CI	Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the PartArt4OW project Consortium. They do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

PartArt4OW has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe
Mission Ocean Programme HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01
Under Grant Agreement No 101157247

Table of contents

List of Acronyms	6
1. Summary	7
2. Methods	7
3. Data Processing and Storage	8
3.1 Storage and Security	8
3.2 Data Collection.....	9
3.2.1 Datasets in PartArt4OW	10
3.2.2 Data about the Ethical Advisor	10
3.2.3 List of external reviewers (WP2) and mentors for applicant PAIs (WP3).....	10
3.2.4 Ambassador Network (WP4, 6).....	11
3.2.5 Applicant details, proposal documents, and reviews (WP1, 2).....	11
3.2.6 Funded PAIs' personal data, contracts, plans, reports and materials.....	12
3.2.7 Impact assessment reports, surveys and interviews (WP4, WP5).....	12
3.2.8 PAIs' activities and their participants, participants to the SailingLab and its contents.....	13
4. FAIR data	14
4.1 Making data findable	14
4.2 Making data openly accessible	14
4.3 Making data interoperable.....	15
4.4 Making data re-usable	15
5. Allocation of resources	15
6.1 Data security	15
7.1 Ethical Aspects	16
7.1 Ethical Guidelines and Compliance.....	16
7.2 Risk Management.....	16
7.3 Mitigation Strategies	17
8. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)	18
9. Conclusions	18
Annex A	20
Annex B	22
Annex C	24
Annex D - EC form for bank details	27

List of Acronyms

Acronym	Name
DEMP	Data and Ethics Management Plan
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
PAIs	Participatory Art Initiatives
PARTART4OW	Participatory Art for society engagement with Ocean and Water
WP	Work Package

Data and Ethics Management Plan

1. Summary

The Data and Ethics Management Plan (DEMP) for the PartArt4OW project outlines procedures to ensure ethical handling of data and artistic outputs, especially in the context of its cascade funding structure. PartArt4OW aims to support third-party organizations and individuals through open calls to produce artistic works that reflect on and strengthen the emotional attachment between society, the oceans and waters. Since the project has just started, this plan addresses the management of data which will be generated both by the project consortium and by third parties (PAIs), while ensuring compliance with ethical standards at each level of the funding and artistic process. To that extent, a permanent ethical advisor has been appointed (Deliverable 7.1).

2. Methods

The PartArt4OW DEMP was developed using the DMP online tool at <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk> and comparing available models such as the one of IMPETUS project (Horizon Europe, EC, under Grant Agreement No 101058677).

It is based on PartArt4OW GA (No 101157247), its amendments and the initial discussions about the implementation of the project carried out during the Kick-off meeting (Oct. 3-4, 2024, Rome, Italy).

A DSA (Data Sharing Agreement) has been signed by the whole Consortium and flanks this Data and Ethics Management Plan.

Non-disclosure rules outlined in the Consortium Agreement (Article 10) amongst partners also apply under the same terms to all external participants to PartArt4OW project activities (reviewers, mentors, ambassadors) that will have access to personal data (name, surname, email addresses and referring institution, if any) of funded PAIs.

The Data and Ethics Management plan contains seven parts.

3. Data Processing and Storage: an overview of the different systems used within PartArt4OW to manage data. This provides also an overview of all datasets currently held or anticipated across all PartArt4OW WPs. It includes details about data sources, formats, the use and storage of data, and any plans for their publication.
4. FAIR data: this provides an overview of how data will be made findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
5. Allocation of resources: this provides an overview of the cost for data processing and how they are covered.
6. Data security: this provides an overview of how data security is ensured, especially with regards to data sharing beyond the projects' boundaries.
7. Ethical aspects: this provides an indication of any ethical considerations related to data management.
8. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).

3. Data Processing and Storage

The processing of all data will follow the principles of GDPR. Data related to other participants (partners and non-partners) involved in the PartArt4OW ecosystem will be stored internally.

3.1 Storage and Security

PartArt4OW uses different data storage and publication platforms for different purposes:

1. **Google Drive** is used to share documents internally with the Consortium. Uniroma1 (PartArt4OW coordinator) has an agreement with Google for using the latter's servers (it can be found here: <https://web.uniroma1.it/gareappalti/sites/default/files/Disp.%202388-2024%20Prot.%20n.%2099485%20del%2027.05.2024-determina%20a%20contrarre.pdf>) in accordance with GDPR and Uniroma's policies about data processing (they can be found here: https://www.uniroma1.it/sites/default/files/field_file_allegati/dr_policy_open_data_0.pdf). PartArt4OW folder on Google Drive is organized through sub-folders that serve for all partners to be aware about project implementation and to have

access to internal-use materials, such as templates for reporting, consortium e-mails and the GA.

Moreover, PartArt4OW Google Drive is also used to store and share internally (the Consortium has signed a Data Sharing Agreement) PAI's contract, plans and reports.

2. **EasyChair** is a GDPR-compliant cloud system with restricted access to authorised personnel only. It will be used to host and manage the Calls for PAIs (Participatory Art Initiatives), including contact information of applicants. Evaluations and scores of proposing PAIs will be stored confidentially, accessible only by authorised personnel.
3. The **Coordinator** will store sensitive data of winning PAIs – such as bank details for contract fulfilment. This data will be required via the EC format and strictly be maintained for internal use only for the duration of the project in a folder in PartArt google Drive that can be accessed by the UniRoma1 team only.
4. A **Zenodo** community will be used to publish outputs, data, papers and resources from the Project and the supported PAIs. We will ask all PAIs to follow Open Science principles. In this sense, we will offer them the opportunity to upload all their outputs on the PartArt4OW Zenodo community, and to share them also at exhibitions such as the Demo days in Barcelona.
5. The mapping of participatory art initiatives for ocean and waters ecosystem will be publicly accessible through **FirstLife**.
6. In addition, PartArt4OW uses an array of communication systems, including the **project website** and social media as described in the Communication Plan (Deliverable number D6.1). A **YouTube** channel (directly connected to the website) is used to upload, collect and share PAI's video and visual products.

3.2 Data Collection

All data collection will comply with EU data protection regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Applicants, third parties and all other participants (such as external experts and ambassadors) are informed of how their data will be used, stored, and shared. Explicit consent will be the base for assessing, storing and processing third parties data (see Annex C).

3.2.1 Datasets in PartArt4OW

- Data about the Ethical Advisor (WP7)
- List of external experts enrolled as reviewers (WP2) and mentors (WP3) for PAIs
- Ambassadors Network (WP4)
- Applicant details, proposal documents, and reviews (WP1, 2)
- PAIs' contracts, plan, and deliverables (WP1, 2, 3)
- Impact assessment reports, surveys, focus groups and interviews (WP4, 5)
- PAI's activities and their participants, participants to the SailingLab and its contents.

3.2.2 Data about the Ethical Advisor

An Ethical Advisor has been appointed by the coordinator of PartArt4OW in fulfilment of WP7. This data consists of name, surname, date of birth, place of residence, fiscal code, email address and telephone number and is stored in .pdf format in the Coordinator's private section of PartArt4OW Google Drive folder. The Ethical Advisor has a regular contract (D7.1) and has reviewed this Data and Ethics Management Plan. She will assess the ethical compliance of winning PAIs' project plans and anticipated outputs.

3.2.3 List of external reviewers (WP2) and mentors for applicant PAIs (WP3)

The list of external experts will be collated in a GDPR-compliant way by T6-Ecosystems which is in charge of appointing them for PAIs reviewing process (WP2). The list will consist of names, email addresses, bank accounts, roles and organisations for experts in various fields relevant to ocean literacy, participatory art and citizen science and participatory process more generally. The list will be held in .xlsx, T6 will request the data and will share it internally with the whole Consortium. External experts will give their consent to this via a specific document (Annex C). They will be engaged in the review process of applicant PAIs and the selection of winners for each call.

Instead, external mentors (WP3) will be selected (one for each PAI) to support selected PAIs in the project implementation process. Their data as well will consist of names, email addresses, roles and organisations and possibly other personal data. The data will be requested via a specific consent form (Annex C) by Epica and shared internally with the whole Consortium. It will only be used internally for the duration of the project.

3.2.4 Ambassador Network (WP4, 6)

The Ambassador Network consists of individual experts, project consortiums and representatives of institutions/associations which will support and interact with PartArt4OW in many ways. Ambassadors will act as experts in the mutual learning exercise, with precise tasks defined throughout WP4 work (Task 4.2). They will support the stakeholder mapping (Task 4.1) and contribute to disseminate the project's open calls and the results of the PAIs.

Data collected through Task 4.1, and particularly the mapping of the participatory art initiatives for ocean and waters ecosystem, will be publicly accessible through FirstLife, a geolocated civic social network developed open access and open source by the University of Turin. Ambassadors will be collated mainly by CMMI and RegNet (which lead WP4 and 6) with the collaboration of all partners. Their data list (obtained through a specific consent form, see Annex C) consists of names, email addresses, roles and organisations for experts in various fields relevant to ocean literacy, participatory art and citizen science. It is held in .xlsx on the shared Google Drive, data will be used internally for the duration of the project and published on PartArt4OW website only under Ambassadors' consent.

3.2.5 Applicant details, proposal documents, and reviews (WP1, 2)

Applications will be collected through the online platform EasyChair, managed - for the PartArt4OW activities, by T6 Ecosystems. We expect applications to be participatory art projects which engage with ocean and water. We also expect researchers, stakeholders, blue economy actors, associations, artists and social activists from European and Associated countries. The data will consist of applicants' names, email and phone details, organisation and role, as well as an application form explaining their proposed project idea, impact, and budget. It will be held primarily on the EasyChair system, with exports in .xlsx, .pdf, .docx format stored on PartArt4OW internal Google Drive. Applications will be shared with reviewers selected from the external experts list for evaluation. All reviewers will be bound by data protection requirements. The data will be used internally, to engage with applications and select the most promising PAIs. Winning PAIs' personal data (name, surname, email address and referring institution, if any) are shared internally with the whole Consortium, while winning PAIs' bank details is collated and stored for

contract fulfilment by UniRoma1 only until all project tasks (including analysis and potential publications) are completed.

3.2.6 Funded PAIs' personal data, contracts, plans, reports and materials.

The consensus for processing funded PAIs' personal data will be requested by the Coordinator with a suitable GDPR-compliant form (Annex C). It is held in .xlsx, .pdf, .docx format on a specific folder in PartArt4OW Google Drive (since the Consortium has signed a Data Sharing Agreement). Same goes for PAI's contracts, work plans and reports.

Before collecting this data, the selection process in WP2 needs to be completed since PAI's proposals are objects of negotiation. The data will consist of project teams' names, email and phone details, organisation and role, as well as a work plan explaining their project idea, prospected impact, and budget. The data will be used internally for contract fulfilment, to engage with and support selected PAIs, as well as to enable the impact assessment report (WP5).

The video and visual materials that the PAI's will produce will be stored in PartArt4OW Google Drive and then uploaded on YouTube, the project website and other social media as outlined in the Communication Plan (Deliverable D6.1).

3.2.7 Impact assessment reports, surveys and interviews (WP4, WP5)

The project will run multiple research-related activities, some in WP4 and other in WP5. With reference to those in WP5, data will be collected directly from engagement with selected PAIs through online questionnaires, interviews and other ad hoc-developed forms. Questionnaires and interviews will ask for respondents' name and role in the PAI; the main focus will be on performed activities, produced outputs and expected and actual socio-economic, artistic, and policy-related impacts. Questions about other impacts such as scientific and technological impacts could be present as well. Questions about the benefits and eventual shortcoming of participating in PartArt4OW will be included too. No direct question on sensitive issues will be included in the questionnaires/interviews/forms; nevertheless we cannot exclude that sensitive data (sexual orientation, political or philosophical ideas, mainly) will be shared by respondents. Data will be reported anonymously with reference to respondents. It will be not possible

to fully anonymize the data because the number of PAIs is limited and each of them will have specific characteristics that will make the relative data recognisable.

PAIs will also be requested to collect data via survey or other methods related to their beneficiaries (i.e participants to PAIs' activities). No personal data will be collected. Questions will be related to participants' opinions on ocean and related challenges, knowledge and skills, opinions on the performed activities, perceived benefits and potential impacts on their behaviours. Demographic data will be collected too (age, gender, employment status, nationality, educational level). All data will be anonymous and will be reported at aggregated level only. This data will be shared with PartArt4OW Consortium and acquired by PAIs through a specific form (Annex B) since it is required to enable and complete the impact assessment in WP5. This data might consist of political and philosophical ideas, health conditions, religious beliefs, sexual orientation and similar might arise. The interview outline will not ask for sensitive information but since a semi-structured interview outline will be used, the interviewed might share sensitive information. This information will be anonymized

Moreover, surveys and focus groups will be carried out also in WP4 to collect and analyse the opinions of the various stakeholders identified through Task 4.1 via a pan-European survey.

All datasets emerging by the above-mentioned research activities will be used for research purposes and will be held in .xlsx, .pdf, .docx, .mp3 and mp4 format on PartArt4OW's shared Google Drive folder.

3.2.8 PAIs' activities and their participants, participants to the SailingLab and its contents.

This data consists of PAI's participants; the documentation (interviews, visual and audio contents, etc) they produce while implementing their projects also for communicative and outreaching purposes; the participants to the Sailing Lab (as interviewed experts, people involved in in-harbour activities, other artists met along the journey of the Lab) and its contents (audio, video, visual about others' intellectual work). The Data concerning PAIs' activity will consist of a wide range of materials (personal data, others' intellectual work) and will be held by each PAI. The Coordinator and her team (UniRoma1) will provide a template (Annex B) for the Informed Consent each PAIs has to use to receive authorization for data processing from involved participants. Since informed consent is

mandatory, PAIs may also provide to their participants another EU GDPR-compliant format (or require informed consent orally) if issues arise in using PartArt4OW's model. The data concerning the Sailing Lab and its contents or participants will instead be held by Sapienza (UniRoma1).

4. FAIR data

The processing of some data (such as audio, visual or video outputs, papers and resources from the PartArt4OW Consortium and the supported PAIs) will follow the principles of the FAIR framework (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

4.1 Making data findable

Any data that we decide to publish will be uploaded and available to the Zenodo community (with an associated URI). It will be used to publish outputs, data, papers and resources from the Project and the supported PAIs. The latter will share their products also at exhibitions such as Demo days in Barcelona. We will publish data about winning PAIs projects and their implementation also on PartArt4OW website, while the mapping of participatory art initiatives for ocean and waters ecosystem will be publicly accessible through FirstLife.

4.2 Making data openly accessible

Winning PAIs will generate text, videos, images, authorship information and further participatory art contents related to ocean and water that will be published on PartArt4OW's website. They will remain accessible also on Zenodo and publicly visible during Demo days in Barcelona. Moreover, the Sailing Lab will produce further visual documentation about ocean and water-related issues and winning PAIs. This data will consist of .mov, .mp4, .jpeg and .png documents which will be available on the project's website.

4.3 Making data interoperable

The published data will use an accessible language (visual, audio or in writing). Moreover they will include and make explicit (such as in the form of citations or description) references to other data.

4.4 Making data re-usable

Where possible, published data is well-described so that it can be replicated and/or combined.

5. Allocation of resources

The only cost associated with data management and publication consists of the website's domain managed by RegNet. We do not currently foresee any other cost. The Zenodo community is free of charge, thus ensuring long-term availability of published data. Any additional required resources will be covered out of the project budget by the partner responsible for the data.

6.1 Data security

All data will be held and kept secure on the project's Google Drive and EasyChair section. These are only accessible to project members and include solutions for backup and recovery. The only personal data that is shared outside of the project consortium is PAIs application data for reviewing processes with external experts. Applicants will consent to the review processes by submitting their application. Practically, data will not be transferred directly, but access to the respective assessment platform will be granted.

7.1 Ethical Aspects

7.1 Ethical Guidelines and Compliance

The PartArt4OW project will strictly follow ethical guidelines in line with Horizon Europe regulations, particularly in handling artistic outputs, respecting intellectual property

rights, and ensuring the ethical treatment of data. The project will adhere to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, GDPR, and national laws of participating countries.

While a board of external and internal experts will be appointed for independent evaluation of proposing PAIs (WP2), an independent Ethical Advisor has been appointed (WP1, 7) to provide guidance on ethical matters throughout the project's duration. The advisor will provide feedback to PartArt4OW, to support the project's adherence to all relevant ethical standards, especially as far as winning PAIs are concerned, since they may explore sensitive or controversial topics.

Key ethical considerations for proposing PAIs include cultural sensitivity, avoidance of harm (emotional, psychological, etc.), environmental sustainability, respect for diversity and inclusion, appropriate safeguarding of staff, participants, and the environment, and informed consent.

7.2 Risk Management

The potential for harm mainly rests in the collection and use of personal data, since PartArt4OW collects primary quantitative and qualitative data about supported initiatives, their engagement and research activities, as well as personal data for the open calls, the support program, stakeholder mapping and engagement, impact assessment and dissemination and outreach activities. Further potential ethical concerns lie with the activities carried out by the supported initiatives (PAIs). As these are going to be selected during the project, it is not possible to say in a precise way what kind of activities they will carry on, what data they will collect, what their objects or who their participants will be.

To that regard, main potential factors of harm might be the misuse of personal data collected through their project (PAI) implementation. Ethical issues can also arise from controversial artistic content and topics.

Moreover, safety concerns may occur since PAIs members and participants will work on/in/around/with water bodies. That could include being in situations where extra care is required, such as assessing weather conditions, or making sure there are no seemingly invisible pitfalls or providing participants with the necessary materials to be safe. The same applies to the Sailing-Lab and those who will take part in it. Since it will take place on and by means of a boat that will be crossing the Mediterranean and docking in some

ports to report about the work of some PAIs, risks may emerge based on weather and sea conditions. So extra care will be needed to carry out the activity safely.

7.3 Mitigation Strategies

PartArt4OW is committed to avoiding any harm through its own activities. Following data minimisation principles, all data collection is limited and conducted appropriately. Data are processed strictly for the purposes it was collected for, in accordance with the GDPR and are stored securely to prevent unauthorised access. Moreover, the same concern will be adopted by supported initiatives (PAIs). PartArt4OW will approach this through a policy of active awareness during the selection of and work with PAIs. In fact, ethical considerations are part of the evaluation criteria and the Calls will include a section with ethical requirements to be ticked by applicants. We will not consider any proposals that have obvious ethical flaws, such as breaching EC requirements for responsible research. We look for proposals that reflect on the ethical dimension of their activities. We will work with the selected PAIs to make them aware of the potential impact they could have on their participants, objects of study, and wider community, and provide guidance for them to mitigate any risks of harm.

In general terms, as far as human participants are concerned, we will:

1. not select PAIs that pose significant risks to their participants or objects of study;
2. support PAIs through training, advice and mentorship in safeguarding citizen scientists and participants;
3. ensure PAIs have sufficient staff and expertise to work with minors where they plan to do so.

One of the partners is based in the UK, meaning that many project activities will be carried out there. We further plan to recruit PAIs from associated countries. All activities by both PartArt itself and the subgrantees will be carried out in accordance with EU legislation.

Moreover, we anticipate that some of our pilots will probably engage in environmental issues, which may include activities touching on endangered flora or fauna. In addition, this will specifically address the life forms and materials that inhabit water, together with its turbulent materiality. We will ensure pilots have sufficient expert support to carry such activities out safely.

Contracts for winner PAIs will be drafted coherently, and all applicant ones will be requested to sign a Declaration of Honour (Annex A). An Informed Consent form (Annex B) will be also provided by the Consortium to winner PAIs so that they can use it while implementing their participatory art initiative in line with GDPR.

8. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

Artists and third-party participants will retain intellectual property rights (IPR) over their works, with an option to grant the project consortium non-exclusive rights for public dissemination, promotion, and archival purposes. Clear agreements will be established with third parties concerning the usage rights and licensing of their artistic works. Any conflict related to IPR will be resolved through arbitration or mediation, with the Ethical Advisor providing oversight to ensure fairness and transparency. A CC-BY (requiring attribution) licence will be used for all project's outputs to ensure that they are shared with minimal restrictions while still enabling us to track impact. All outputs of the PAIs in the accelerator remain under their IPR and control, though we will encourage open access or open-source models and require data to be published openly where feasible.

9. Conclusions

The PartArt4OW project is committed to upholding the highest standards of data management and ethical conduct, especially in relation to its cascade funding nature. The Data and Ethics Management Plan is reviewed by the appointed Ethical Advisor. By fostering a transparent and ethically sound process, the project seeks to empower third parties while safeguarding the integrity of research and artistic outputs. Sustainability, inclusivity and mutual learning are key features of the project's approach and mission.

Annex A

Declaration of honour

1. I declare:

- a. the organisation that I represent is not bankrupt or being wound up, is not having its affairs administered by the courts, has not entered into an arrangement with creditors, has not suspended business activities, is not the subject of proceedings concerning those matters, nor is in any analogous situation arising from a similar procedure provided for in national legislation or regulations;
- b. neither the organisation that I represent nor persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been convicted of an offence concerning their professional conduct by a judgment which has the force of res judicata;
- c. neither the organisation that I represent nor persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been guilty of grave professional misconduct proven by any means which the contracting authority can justify including by decisions of the European Investment Bank and international organisations;
- d. the organisation that I represent is in compliance with its obligations relating to the payment of social security contributions or the payment of taxes in accordance with the legal provisions of the country in which it is established or with those of the country of the contracting authority or those of the country where the contract is to be performed;
- e. neither the organisation that I represent nor persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been the subject of a judgement which has the force of res judicata for fraud, corruption, involvement in a criminal organisation or any other illegal activity, where such illegal activity is detrimental to the Union's financial interests;
- f. the organisation that I represent is not subject to an administrative penalty for being guilty of misrepresenting the information required by the contracting authority as a condition of participation in a grant award procedure or another procurement procedure or failing to supply this information, or having been declared to be in serious breach of its obligations under contracts or grants covered by the Union's budget;
- g. the proposed project does not receive funding for the same activities from other sources.

2. I declare that I:

- a. am not subject to a conflict of interest;
- b. have not made false declarations in supplying the information required as a condition of participation in the PartArt4OW call or did not fail to supply this information;

- c. am not in one of the situations of exclusion, referred to in the above-mentioned points 1a) to 1f).
- d. I am an individual or organization located within an EU or in an Associated Country, following Horizon Europe funding eligibility rules. I am not, nor do I represent an entity subject to EU restrictive measures under Article 29 of the Treaty on the European Union (TEU) and Article 215 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU) not eligible to participate as recipients of FSTP.
- e. Proposed project will be implemented in the EU or an associated country.

3. I certify that I:

- a. am committed to participate in the project;
- b. have stable and sufficient sources of funding to maintain activity throughout participation in the project and to provide any counterpart funding necessary;
- c. have or will have the necessary resources as and when needed to carry out involvement in the project.

4. I declare that I and other representatives of my organisation will:

- a. ensure the quality, integrity and accuracy of research activities and outputs within the scope of the project;
- b. ensure informed consent of any and all volunteers taking part in the project, both data subjects (such as in the case of surveys) and project participants (such as citizen scientists);
- c. take all steps to protect and ensure the confidentiality of all project participants;
- d. take all necessary steps to protect vulnerable groups who may participate within the project (particularly minors and those with a reduced capacity for consent);
- e. actively seek to encourage participation from underrepresented groups;
- f. comply with any and all legal requirements, both within the country or countries in which the project shall operate and at the European level, in particular the European Union General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679;
- g. Be committed to key RRI (Responsible Research and innovation) concerns and to the Climate Pact Pledge and the Make Europe Blue Campaign.
- h. take all reasonable steps to ensure project outputs are made openly available and accessible to the widest possible audience, where this does not infringe upon the rights and expectations of project participants or contravene the legal requirements of the territories in which the project shall operate.

I declare that, to the best of my knowledge and belief, I am eligible to apply for the PartArt4OW call and all the information I provided in the form is true.

Name	
Signature	
Date	

--	--

Annex B

This is for the data that funded PAIs will acquire from the participants in their activities. This form is to be held by PAIs' referents for 5 years and should not be sent to the Coordinator. *Texts in italics are indicative of the content of the section and should be rewritten according to PAI's and their participants' requirements.* NOTE: This document should be shared with and signed by anyone you invite to contribute data, as an artist, a citizen scientist, or a participant who engages with your participatory art project in other ways. If you collect different types of data, or engage with different persons or communities, you may need separate documents for each case.

Information sheet template

What this project is about

[Give a brief overview of your project that people new to your project can understand.]

What we invite you to do

[Explain what you want your participants to do. Be as detailed as possible and explain things like where they need to go (e.g. your office, a harbour, a lake), what equipment they need (e.g. smartphones, waterproof clothes), and what they should do (e.g. take a photo of plastics)]

What data we are collecting from you

[Include all the data you want them to contribute. This data may include but is not limited to:

- *personal data (name, surname, email address and referring institution, if any);*
- *video or photo showing the image of somebody;*
- *audio recordings including voices, music or else;*
- *drawings;*
- *biological data*
- *....*

Please remember that release forms must be carried and used at all times in the event of filming children and people in close up or making interviews (not necessary for public figures i.e. politicians). The consent of a person to be filmed must be in writing and signed, you can use the release form model indicated HERE BELOW. Minors cannot be filmed on face unless

the release form will be signed by the parents or the legal guardian, in this case the ID's data of the parent must be also fully reported on the form itself]

What we will do with this data

[Explain what you plan to do, how data will be processed, stored, analysed and/or published. For example:

- *we will store, use and publish this data according to the EU GDPR;*
- *...]*

Why does this matter

[Explain how doing this will benefit your participants' ocean or water literacy or how it is aligned with their needs. You can explain this together with what you want the participatory art project overall to achieve with this data]

What could go wrong

[Explain to your participants how what you plan to do might cause harm, to themselves, to others, or to their environment. It is important that you think seriously about any risks that might occur (e.g. they could fall off a boat), how to minimise these risks (e.g. you provide safety gear), and what would to do if they happen after all (e.g. contact insurance)].

Personal and Sensitive data

[Explain what data you collect about your participants, what you do with this data, and how they can have this data removed (e.g. by contacting someone in your team. Data such as names, surnames, phone numbers or email addresses are personal data. Information concerning sex life or sexual orientation, racial or ethnic origin, political opinion, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, genetic data, health data or financial information (bank account numbers) are sensitive data].

Consent form template

The undersigned..... , born in date
resident in.....Country.....ID.....

Having read the Privacy Policy pursuant to and for the purposes of art. 13 of EU Regulation no. 2016/679 "General Data Protection Regulation" (so-called GDPR)¹

¹ "In order to ensure a consistent level of protection for natural persons throughout the Union and to prevent divergences hampering the free movement of personal data within the internal market, a Regulation is necessary to provide legal

Declares

- 1) To have read and understood the information sheet. I have had the opportunity to consider the information and ask questions which have been answered to my satisfaction.
- 2) That I and/or my son and/or the minor under my guardianship volunteer to be a participant/contribute to this participatory art project and understand that I and/or my son and/or the minor under my guardianship can drop out of it at any time.
- 3) That I understand that the project may process my personal information (and/or of my son and/or the minor under my guardianship) for the purposes explained in the Information sheet. All information will be handled in accordance with applicable local laws and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- 4) I understand that my data (and/or my son and/or the minor under my guardianship) may be used for the purpose of.....
...
5) That I understand that the non-personal data I (and/or my son and/or the minor under my guardianship) contribute to the project may be published under open science principles.
- 6) to agree to be portrayed/filmed/recorded by the contact person*[name of the contact person]*..... of the Project*[name of the project]*..... in date..... with my full and unconditional consent, or in the case of a minor with the consent of the parent or legal guardian.
- 7) That the images/video footage/audio-video recordings for which I have given consent will be provided to PartArt4OW and their partners for promotional and informational purposes related to the project itself.

certainty and transparency for economic operators, including micro, small and medium-sized enterprises, and to provide natural persons in all Member States with the same level of legally enforceable rights and obligations and responsibilities for controllers and processors, to ensure consistent monitoring of the processing of personal data, and equivalent sanctions in all Member States as well as effective cooperation between the supervisory authorities of different Member States. The proper functioning of the internal market requires that the free movement of personal data within the Union is not restricted or prohibited for reasons connected with the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data. To take account of the specific situation of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises, this Regulation includes a derogation for organisations with fewer than 250 employees with regard to record-keeping. In addition, the Union institutions

and bodies, and Member States and their supervisory authorities, are encouraged to take account of the specific needs of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises in the application of this Regulation. The notion of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises should draw from Article 2 of the Annex to Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC" (art. 13 of EU Regulation no. 2016/679 "General Data Protection Regulation").

Annex C

This is for all Partners that will engage PartArt4OW-related activities which involve the usage of personal data. It is to be signed by all external participants to the following activities: contract fulfilment, Sailing Lab, Ecosystem Building, Ambassador Network, Mentoring, Reviewing, Communication and Dissemination. NOTE: It is to be customized according to specific activities, type of data and participants.

Information note according to art.13 of EU Regulation N. 679/2016 of 27.04.2016

Data Controller

The Data Controller is:

- SAPIENZA UNIVERSITY OF ROME (data controller); the Director. Contact: direttorememotef@uniroma1.it . PEC: dip.memotef@cert.uniroma1.it.
- CMMI CYPRUS MARINE AND MARITIME INSTITUTE (CMMI), PIC 899786163, established in ATHINON 38 DEMOTIKO MEGARO, LARNACA 6300, Cyprus. Contact: maria.hadjimichael@cmmi.blue.
- REGENERA NETWORK S.L. (REGNET), PIC 884460454, established in AVDA- JUAN GRANDE, 8, MALAGA 29014, Spain. Contact: dopico.carolina@gmail.com.
- T6 Ecosystems srl, PIC 999529614, established in Via Aureliana 63, Rome 00187, Italy. Contact: a.nicolai@t-6.it.
- RAW-NEWS, Raw Visuals Ltd Company (RAW-NEWS), PIC 880827707, established in Street C/O Semaphore Consulting Hill House 1 Smiths C, CM16 6BD, Thornwood, Epping Essex, United Kingdom. Contact: federico.fornaro@raw-news.net.
- FUNDACION EPICA LA FURA DELS BAUS (EPICA), PIC 901515188, established in Calle Pujades, Num 77, Planta 2, Puerta 6, BARCELONA 08005, Spain. Contact: fran@fundacionepica.org.

Purposes and Legal Basis for Data Processing

The processing of personal data (name, surname, email address and referring institution, if any) of PAIS' leaders and of other external participants (such as reviewers, mentors and ambassadors) and data generated during the activity (eg. video, photo, audio recordings, music, text, graphic, drawing...) is necessary to carry out the envisaged project activities (Contract Fulfillment, Sailing Lab, Accelerator Program, Impact assessment, Ecosystem building, Communication, Dissemination and Outreaching) in the framework of EC

funded Horizon Europe Project PartArt4OW (Participatory Art for Society Engagement with Ocean and Water - Grant Agreement No: 101157247).

Nature of Data Conferral and Consequences of Refusal

The conferral of personal data (eg. name, surname, email address and referring institution, if any) and data generated during the activity (eg. video, photo, audio recordings, music, text, graphic, drawing, ...) to Università di Roma (La Sapienza), T6 Ecosystems, Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute, Regenera network, Raw-News and Fundacion Epica - La Fura dels Baus is mandatory to be involved in the above-outlined project activities.

The refusal to give authorization for the processing of the data causes the inability to participate in the activities of PartArt4OW.

Data Processing Procedure and Authorised Data Managers

The processing of data is performed by a digital and computer based procedure by members of Università di Roma (La Sapienza), T6 Ecosystems, Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute, Regenera network, Raw-news and Fundacion Epica involved in PartArt4OW.

The data will be processed in order to implement the aforementioned project activities. Some data could be published on PartArt4OW website.

In any case, the data will not be used for direct sales, market research or commercial communications for generating profits.

Data Subject Rights

Data Subjects can request the Data Controller indicated above, if conditions apply, for access to personal data as per Art. 15 of the Regulation, to amend data as per Art. 16 of the Regulation, to erase data as per Art. 17 of the Regulation, or to limit the processing of data as per Art. 19 of the Regulation. The Data Subject can oppose processing of data as per Art. 21 of the Regulation and can request data transferral as per Art 20 of the Regulation. In case of Regulation violations, the Data Subject can present a complaint to the Data Protection Authority.

I confirm that I have read the Information pursuant to art. 13 of the EU Regulation n. 679/2016 of 27/04/2016 and I agree to the processing of the data.

Date _____

Signed _____

Annex D - EC form for bank details

FINANCIAL IDENTIFICATION

PRIVACY STATEMENT https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/about_the_european_commission/eu_budget/privacy_statement_en.pdf
By submitting this form, you acknowledge that you have been informed about the processing of your personal data by the European Commission for accounting and contractual purposes.

Please use CAPITAL LETTERS and LATIN CHARACTERS when filling in the form.

BANKING DETAILS ①	
ACCOUNT NAME ②	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
IBAN/ACCOUNT NUMBER ③	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
CURRENCY	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
BIC/SWIFT CODE	<input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/> BRANCH CODE ④ <input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/>
BANK NAME	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
ADDRESS OF BANK BRANCH	
STREET & NUMBER	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
TOWN/CITY	<input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/> POSTCODE <input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/>
COUNTRY	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>

ACCOUNT HOLDER'S DATA AS DECLARED TO THE BANK	
ACCOUNT HOLDER	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
STREET & NUMBER	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
TOWN/CITY	<input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/> POSTCODE <input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/>
COUNTRY	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>

REMARK	<input style="width: 85%;" type="text"/>
--------	--

BANK STAMP + SIGNATURE OF BANK REPRESENTATIVE ⑤	DATE (Obligatory)
	SIGNATURE OF ACCOUNT HOLDER (Obligatory)

- ① Enter the final bank data and not the data of the intermediary bank.
- ② This does not refer to the type of account. The account name is usually the one of the account holder. However, the account holder may have chosen to give a different name to its bank account.
- ③ Fill in the IBAN Code (International Bank Account Number) if it exists in the country where your bank is established
- ④ Only applicable for US (ABA code), for AU/NZ (BSB code) and for CA (Transit code). Does not apply for other countries.
- ⑤ It is preferable to attach a copy of RECENT bank statement. Please note that the bank statement has to confirm all the information listed above under 'ACCOUNT NAME', 'ACCOUNT NUMBER/IBAN' and 'BANK NAME'. With an attached statement, the stamp of the bank and the signature of the bank's representative are not required. The signature of the account-holder and the date are ALWAYS mandatory.